

MORPHOLOGICAL AND ANATOMICAL STUDY OF RHIZOMES OF *DIOSCOREA NIPPONICA* MAKINO

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Аннотация. *Dioscorea nipponica* Makino. ning ildizpоясини морфологик ва анатомик тузилиши ўрганилди. Тадқиқот натижасида кам шохланганлик, арқонсимон илдизлари, яхши ривожланган пўстлоқ, ўтказувчи бойламлар тузилиши, паренхима хужайралари, илдизпоянинг узунлиги бўйлаб рафидли бойламларини мавжудлиги, крахмал доналарининг шакли ва ҳажми каби морфологик ва анатомик диагностик белгилар аниқланди.

Калит сўзлар: морфология, анатомия, доривор ўсимлик, илдизпоя, *Dioscorea nipponica* Makino.

Аннотация. Изучены морфологические и анатомические строение корневищ *Dioscorea nipponica* Makino. По результатам исследования выявлены морфологические и анатомические диагностические показатели, как, мало разветвленное, шнуrowидные корни, опробовавшая кора, строение проводящих пучков, клеток паренхимы, наличие пучков рафид ориентированных по длине корневища, форма и размер крахмальных зерен.

Ключевые слова: морфология, анатомия, лекарственная растения, корневище, *Dioscorea nipponica* Makino.

Abstract. Morphological and anatomical structures of *Dioscorea nipponica* Makino rhizomes were studied. According to the results of the study morphological and anatomical diagnostic parameters such as, little branched, cord-like roots, pollenized bark, structure of conducting bundles, parenchyma cells, presence of raphid bundles oriented along the length of rhizome, shape and size of starch grains were revealed.

Keywords: morphology, anatomy, medicinal plant, rhizome, *Dioscorea nipponica* Makino.

The genus *Dioscorea* L. includes more than 650 species, which are not present in the flora of Uzbekistan. *Dioscorea nipponica* Makino. - is a dicotyledonous liana growing in Russia, Japan, China and Southeast Asia [1]. In Uzbekistan, this plant is available only in the Botanical Garden in Tashkent, also an unstudied introduced plant.

Rhizome of this species of *Dioscorea* is authorized for medical use in Russia, China, Korea, and Japan. In the first half of the last century, the medical use of *Dioscorea* was limited. Tincture of rhizomes and roots of *Dioscorea* was part of a complex preparation “Cholelitin” №1, recommended for the treatment of biliary stone disease. Scientific and practical interest in the plant genus *Dioscorea* appeared in the 60-70s of the XX century as a source of diosgenin used in the production of corticosteroid drugs. Due to the low content of diosgenin, the raw material of *Dioscorea nipponica* in Russia was used to produce the drug “Polysponin”, which is a sum of water-soluble steroidal saponins and is used as a hypocholesterolemic agent [2].

In China, the powder of underground organs of *Dioscorea nipponica*, decoction and alcohol tincture are used for medicinal purposes for oral intake. Indications for use are: rheumatic arthritis, tendon sprains, chronic bronchitis, asthma, etc. In Korea, the raw material of *Dioscorea nipponii* is used in the form of a decoction. In Korea, raw material *Dioscorea nipponese* in the form of decoction is prescribed in the complex treatment of diabetes mellitus.

Rhizomes of *Dioscorea suprotivaya* are used in traditional Chinese medicine (TCM) for diseases of the stomach, spleen, anorexia with chronic diarrhea, a number of urological diseases, etc [3].

Currently, the Russian pharmaceutical market has a large number of biologically active supplements (BAA), which include dry extract of dioscorea (Wild Yam, dioscorea pills, Liver-Place, Pro-G-Yam NSP, solid suspension, “Dobryj Molodets”, etc.). The main indications for the use of these dietary supplements are: regulation of female sex glands, osteoporesis, reduction of blood cholesterol levels, normalization of blood pressure, etc. [4].

Dioscorea nipponica Makino. -A perennial herbaceous liana with curly stems up to 4 m long, rarely more. Leaves are 6-12 cm long, alternate, petiolate, broadly ovate with a heart-shaped base. Lower leaves are seven-lobed, with short lateral lobes and a larger, elongated, pointed middle lobe. The upper leaves are three to five-lobed or with hardly expressed lobes. Leaf blades are shortly pubescent or in some forms densely and softly pubescent from below.

Flowers are unisexual, dicotyledonous, about 3 mm in diameter, with simple corolla-like, deeply six-divided, yellowish-greenish perianth. Stamen flowers are usually clustered 3-7 in semi-zontics forming simple, less often branched axillary clusters. Stamens are 6, attached to perianth, pistil is reduced. Pistillate flowers are collected in a simple brush with 1 pistil and 6 reduced stamens. Pistil with lower three-lobed ovary, short column and 3 stigmas.

Fruit is an almost sessile, three-nested, broadly elliptic boll, 1.6-2.5 cm long, with 3 broad wings on the ribs and a notch at the apex. Seeds are flat, with a long, thinly webbed, upwardly retracted wing, the length of the seed without wing is 5-7 mm, width 2-4 mm [5]. The plant flowers in July-August, seeds ripen in August-October.

The rhizome is horizontal, located shallowly from the soil surface, thick (1-fig.).

1- fig.: General view of the rhizome of *Dioscorea nipponica* Makino.

Low branched, up to 1.5 m long and 2 cm in diameter, with traces of dead stems, with thin, rigid, cord-like roots throughout. The peeling outer layer of the rhizome bark is easily separated as a thin, dark-colored, flaking film. The stems are few, simple, glabrous.

Rhizome pieces are up to 30 cm long and 2 cm thick, simple, cylindrical, entire, slightly curved or twisted inside. The surface, weakly longitudinally wrinkled, with well-marked remnants of dead stems, is covered with a thin layer of cork, which usually peels off easily. Few elastic thin roots, up to 40 cm long and about 1 mm thick, emerge from the rhizomes. The fracture of the rhizomes is smooth, white and light yellow in color. Rhizomes and roots are light brown or yellowish, turning yellow after the cork peels off. The odor is faint, characteristic. Young rhizome sections are more fleshy, elastic, with large buds.

Anatomical structures of *Dioscorea nipponica* Makino rhizome were studied.

The rhizome of *Dioscorea nipponica* Makino. was fixed in 70% ethanol according to the generally recognized method and its anatomical structure was studied on a transverse section of the fixed material [6].

Preparations prepared by cutting the cross section by hand and Motic B1 microscope were used to study the anatomical features. The preparations were stained with safranin. Cells and tissues were measured using a MOB-15 micrometer.

Quantitative measurements of several traits: diameter and thickness of rhizome, width of cork, height of endoderm, length and width of parenchyma, thickness of storage tissue and conductive bundles were performed according to the generally accepted method [7].

Statistical analysis of the data was calculated with a personal computer (MS Excel) using generally accepted methods. Microphotographs were taken using a digital camera, and mathematical analysis was performed using a Motic microscope.

When examining a transverse section of the rhizome, a cork is visible, and below it there is a narrow strip of cortex consisting of small, tangentially elongated cells with nonwoody sheaths (2-figures, Table).

2- fig: Anatomical structures of *Dioscorea nipponica* Makino.:
A - general view, B - cortex, C - storage tissue.

Table

Anatomical parameters of the rhizome of *Dioscorea nipponica* Makino.

	Characteristics	Indices, μm
	Rhizome diameter	19,3±0,5
	Cork width	6,1±0,2
	Height of endoderm	5,3±0,3
	Length of parenchyma	9,3±0,2
	Parenchyma width	10,5±0,3
	Reserve tissue thickness	13,3±0,4
	Thickness of conductive bundles	12,5±0,4

Large cortex cells contain calcium oxalate raphides oriented along the rhizome. A narrow strip of cortex consists of small, tangentially elongated cells with nonwoody sheaths. Individual, larger cells contain bundles of raphides about 110 μm long, oriented strictly along the rhizome. The endoderm is indistinctly expressed. The central cylinder occupies most of the rhizome, consists of parenchyma cells, among which closed collateral conductive bundles are arranged in

no particular order. Rhizome parenchyma consists of large, polygonal cells densely adjoining each other. Starch grains, different in shape (slightly angular, ellipse-shaped or rounded) are found in large numbers in the cells of the parenchyma; their diameter varies from 9.3 to 10.5 μm . The cell envelopes are odontogenic, with numerous large pores. Closed collateral bundles are located in the central cylinder, small, slightly radially elongated at the periphery, large, almost rounded in outline closer to the center. Vessel walls are dense, containing numerous fringed pores. Parenchyma is almost completely absent in xylem.

The table shows that rhizome diameter is $19.3 \pm 0.5 \mu\text{m}$, plugs are square shaped and small $6.1 \pm 0.2 \mu\text{m}$. The parenchyma is rounded and the size of length and width are close figures. The thickness of the storage tissue is $13.3 \pm 0.4 \mu\text{m}$ and the thickness of the conductive bundles is $12.5 \pm 0.4 \mu\text{m}$.

Morphological and diagnostic features were revealed: little branched, cord-like roots, pollinated bark, structure of conducting bundles, parenchyma cells, presence of raphid bundles oriented along the rhizome length, shape and size of starch grains.

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